

Influence of Humic and Fulvic acids on the Availability and Inorganic Transformation of Phosphorus in soil

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The effects of humic and fulvic acids on the availability of phosphates and inorganic transformation of added water soluble phosphate in four soils of varied characteristics were studied. Available phosphorus contents of the soils were determined by chemical methods. Humic and fulvic acids greatly increased the availability of phosphorus both in phosphate treated and untreated soils. Application of these acids solubilised the native phosphates of iron, aluminium and calcium and minimised the transformation of added water soluble phosphate into iron phosphate, aluminium phosphate and calcium phosphate. The effect of fulvic acid in these respects was more pronounced than that of humic acid.

WATER soluble phosphates, when added to soil, are transformed into insoluble compounds and the nature and magnitude of such transformation is influenced by the chemical characteristics of the soils. The availability is largely determined by the following factors: (a) Soil pH¹, (b) soluble iron, aluminium

Experimental

The soils used were collected from Agricultural farms at (i) Jaguli (alluvial), (ii) Naksalbari (acidic), (iii) Sriniketan (laterite) and (iv) Canning (saline). Table 1 gives relevant characteristics of the soils used.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Soils	pH	Organic C(%)	Sp. conductivity (m mhos/cm)	C.E.C. me/100g	Exch. Ca me/100g	P fixing capacity mgP/100g	%Clay
Canning	7.3	0.580	8.00	25.2	11.6	335	37
Jaguli	6.5	0.900	0.16	26.3	16.2	390	47
Sriniketan	4.8	0.650	0.10	8.0	4.2	370	33
Naxalbari	5.0	1.070	0.04	10.8	5.2	290	40

and manganese^{2,3}, (c) available calcium and calcium minerals⁴, (d) amount and decomposition of organic matter^{1,5} and (e) activities of microorganisms.

The application of organic matter is known to affect the concentrations of active forms of iron and aluminium which are normally present in substantial quantity in the soils⁶ and therefore, are likely to influence the transformation of applied phosphate in these soils and consequently its availability to crops. Shapiro⁷ showed that organic matter increased availability of synthetic iron and aluminium phosphates applied to acid soils under waterlogged condition. Savant and Ellis⁸ also showed that the availability of applied phosphorous in waterlogged soils was markedly increased by the addition of organic matter. Mandal⁶ showed that organic matter and liming markedly influenced the transformation of native phosphorous in soil under waterlogged condition. Mandal and Mandal⁹ also showed that the application of both organic matter and lime lowered significantly the fixation of phosphorous as aluminium and iron phosphates in acidic soils.

The influence of organic matter on the availability of applied phosphorous may be best understood if the effect of different fractions of humus on the inorganic transformation of phosphorous applied is known. The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken with the object to study the effect of humic acids and fulvic acids on the availability of applied phosphate and on its inorganic transformation in some soils of West Bengal.

Humus was collected from peat and fractionated to humic and fulvic acids by the method described earlier.¹⁰ Humic acid was dialysed as such against distilled water and fulvic acid was transformed to Ba-fulvate and dialysed. The dialysed Ba-fulvate was transformed to H-form by passing through IR-120 resin (II). Phosphorous was added to the soils in the form of KH₂PO₄ solution at the rate of 200 ppm. 10 g. of each soil were taken in small plastic container and incubated for 22 days at 50 per cent of the water holding capacity of the soils at 35°±1° with the following treatments.

1. Control (po)
2. Soil+200 ppm p(p)
3. Soil+Humic acid (poH)
4. Soil + 200 ppm P+Humic acid (PH)
5. Soil+Fulvic acid (poF)
6. Soil+200 ppm P+Fulvic acid (PF)

Humic and Fulvic acids were added at the rate of 0.05 g/10 g. soil. After 22 days, the samples were taken out, dried at room temperature and ground to 100 mesh and available phosphorous was determined (in duplicate) by Olsen's method.¹¹ The phosphorous extracted by Bray's No. 1 reagent was also determined. In another set of experiment 1 g portion of the sample (in duplicate) was taken for fractionation of inorganic phosphates by the method proposed by Chang and

Jackson¹². Total phosphorous present in humic and fulvic acids was also determined after perchloric acid digestion.

Results and Discussion

The amounts of available phosphorous extracted by Olsen's method and by Bray's No. 1 reagent from the untreated and treated samples of the four soils are given in Table 2 and Table 3. The results show that after 22 days' incubation the phosphate which was added in the form of KH_2PO_4 was converted considerably in the insoluble form. When Olsen's reagent (NaHCO_3 solution) was used, the amount of phosphorous extracted from the soils followed the order :

TABLE 2—AVAILABLE PHOSPHOROUS IN PPM BY OLSEN'S METHOD

Soils treatments	Canning	Jaguli	Sriniketan	Naxalbari
po	2.9	nil	12.9	5.7
p	37.1	28.6	51.4	43.3
poH	7.1	8.6	15.7	8.0
pH	41.4	35.7	55.7	56.4
poF	132.9	84.3	145.7	102.6
pF	148.6	107.1	178.6	116.3

TABLE 3—AVAILABLE PHOSPHOROUS IN PPM BY BRAY'S METHOD

Soils Treatments	Canning	Jaguli	Sriniketan	Naxalbari
po	12.0	9.5	1.5	13.0
p	115.0	42.5	19.0	47.5
poH	17.0	17.5	2.5	19.5
pH	92.0	51.5	23.0	60.0
poF	130.0	81.5	110.0	113.0
pF	180.0	131.0	145.0	140.0

Sriniketan > Naksalbari > Canning > Jaguli
 But for the Bray's No.1 reagent the sequence was
 Canning > Naksalbari > Jaguli > Sriniketan

On addition of humic and fulvic acids, the available phosphorous content in the soils was considerably increased, which may be due to the solubilisation of native insoluble inorganic phosphorous compounds in soils by these acids and partly due to the mineralisation of organic phosphorous contained in these acids (total phosphorous present in humic acid was 2860 ppm and in fulvic, acid 6880 ppm). The increases were more with fulvic acid than with humic acid. The results are in agreement with the findings of Leaver and Russell¹ who found that if the soil was treated with suitable humic acid extract, the phosphate holding power of the soil was reduced markedly. The ability of humus and lignin to reduce the phosphate fixation was also shown by Sieling⁵ who showed that both humus and lignin are effective, the humus to the greater degree. The results of Sieling suggest that mineral fixation of phosphorous may be lower in soils comparatively high in organic matter.

Tables 2 and 3 also show that for solubilising the native insoluble inorganic phosphorous, fulvic acid is superior to humic acid. This may be due to the greater chelating power of fulvic acid. Strictly humus substances have the ability to form complex and intracomplex compounds (chelates) with iron, aluminium and other polyvalent ions. This ability is determined to a

considerable extent by the presence in their molecules of hydrophilic groups situated in side radicals^{13,14}. It is for this reason that fulvic acids have the greatest tendency to form intracomplex compounds with a number of cations, notably iron because of its more hydrophilic nature. However, humic acids also take part in the formation of complex compounds. Humic and fulvic acids can easily form chelates with Ca, Fe and Al which are responsible for the fixation of phosphates and thus reduce the intensity of fixation of phosphorous by these elements. The results also show that the amount of the available phosphate extracted by Bray's No.1 reagent is higher than that extracted by Olsen's method, except in the case of the soil of Sriniketan. This is partly due to more solubilisation of the insoluble Al- and Ca-phosphates by Bray's reagent. The low value for Sriniketan soil may be due to the fact that this soil is laterite in nature and therefore most of the phosphate present in this soil remains as insoluble Fe-PO_4 and the added phosphate is mostly fixed as Fe-PO_4 which is not recovered by Bray's reagent.

Data in Table 4 show the distribution of native phosphates and transformation of added water soluble phosphate into different inorganic forms in the four soils under study. A general trend in relative amounts

TABLE 4—DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF PHOSPHATE IN THE SOILS (PPM P)

Treatments	Canning Soil			
	Saloid bound P	Al-P	Fe-P	Ca-P
po	nil	5.8	50.0	60.0
p	7.3	55.5	100.0	75.0
difference	7.3	49.7	50.0	15.0
poH	0.8	20.0	50.0	75.0
pH	11.5	58.5	80.0	90.0
difference	10.7	38.5	30.0	15.0
poF	87.0	173.8	125.0	85.0
pF	102.5	252.3	130.0	95.0
difference	15.5	78.5	5.0	10.0
Jaguli Soil				
po	0.0	0.5	40.0	45.0
p	0.0	2.8	80.0	65.0
difference	0.0	2.3	40.0	20.0
poH	2.8	2.8	50.0	35.0
pH	4.3	4.3	95.0	55.0
difference	1.5	1.5	45.0	20.0
poF	71.3	2.8	120.0	65.0
pF	111.3	4.3	120.0	75.0
difference	40.0	1.5	0.0	5.0
Sriniketan Soil				
po	4.3	25.0	57.2	0.0
p	7.8	89.3	160.7	15.0
difference	3.5	64.3	103.5	15.0
poH	5.0	39.3	60.7	0.0
pH	10.5	78.5	142.9	35.0
difference	5.5	39.2	82.2	35.0
poF	24.3	190.8	187.7	20.0
pF	31.3	228.5	250.0	15.0
difference	7.0	37.7	62.7	-5.0
Naksalbari Soil				
po	24.3	11.5	45.0	130.0
p	55.5	14.3	55.0	165.0
difference	31.2	2.8	10.0	35.0
poH	24.3	12.8	45.0	130.0
pH	87.0	17.0	45.0	145.0
difference	62.7	4.2	0.0	15.0
poF	125.5	22.8	45.0	110.0
pF	316.3	20.0	40.0	130.0
difference	190.8	-2.8	-5.0	20.0

of native aluminium phosphate (Al-P), iron phosphate (Fe-P) and calcium phosphate (Ca-P) in the soils shows that Fe-P dominates in Sriniketan soil (laterite), but Ca-P dominates in other three soils. Application of humic and fulvic acids increased the amount of all the forms of phosphate both in phosphate treated and untreated soils. This may be attributed to the mineralisation of organic phosphates added through humic and fulvic acids and subsequent transformation of the released phosphate in different forms.

With similar treatments the difference between the phosphate treated and untreated samples has been considered as the transformation of added phosphate in different forms. Data disclose that the recovery of added phosphate as saloid bound form (NH₄Cl extractable-P) in untreated soils is partly associated with the phosphate fixing capacity of the soils. From 200 ppm of applied P, the recovery of P as saloid bound phosphate was 7.3, 0.35 and 31.2 ppm in Canning, Jaguli, Sriniketan and Naxalbari soils respectively. Application of humic and fulvic acids increased the recovery of added P as saloid bound phosphate markedly. The increases may be attributed to the chelating action of humic and fulvic acids, and because of the greater chelating power, the action of fulvic acid is more. Table 4 also shows that the total recovery of added phosphate as saloid bound P, Al-P, Fe-P and Ca-P was less than that applied. This was probably due to the transformation of the added phosphate to forms not extractable by the reagents used.

Application of humic and fulvic acids considerably minimised the fixation of added phosphate as Al-P, except in Canning soil. This is due to inactivation of aluminium by chelating action of humic and fulvic acids. The decomposition of these acids also produces some low molecular weight organic acids, which are likely to form insoluble compounds with aluminium, and thus reduce the intensity of fixation of phosphate by this element. Less transformation of added phosphate as Al-P in

presence of fulvic acid than in presence of humic acid is likely due to greater chelating power of fulvic acid.

Humic acid and fulvic acid considerably reduced the transformation of added phosphate to Fe-P and in this case also fulvic acid was found to be superior to humic acid. These acids as such or their decomposition products, as mentioned earlier, form complex compounds with iron and thus reduce the intensity of fixation of phosphorus by this element. Application of these humus acids significantly reduced the fixation of phosphorus as Ca-P, but the effect was not so pronounced as was in the case of fixation as aluminium and iron phosphates.

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